

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1890	Herman Karl Haeberlin	1910	1914	1918		German-American anthropologist and linguist	1890-1918
1890	Ernst W. Selmer	1913	1913	1960		Norwegian philologist and phonetician	1890-1971
1890	Benno Landsberger	1913	1913	1955		German Assyriologist	1890-1968
1890	Kurt Badt	1913	1913	1937		German art historian	1890-1973
1890	Ernst Lohmeyer	1913	1914	1946		German scholar of the New Testament, Protestant theologian and Bible professor	1890-1946
1890	Heinrich Zimmer	1914	1914	1943		German Indologist and linguist (Indian philology), historian of South Asian art	1890-1943
1890	Fran Ramovš	1914	1914	1952		Slovenian linguist	1890-1952
1890	Fritz Saxl	1915		1948		Austrian-British art historian	1890-1948
1890	Archer Taylor	1915	1915	1958		American foremost specialists in American and European folklore	1890-1973
1890	Eino Kaila	1916	1916	1958		Finnish scholar (psychology (sometimes considered to be the founder of Finnish psychology), physics and theater, and attempted to find unifying principles behind various branches of human and natural sciences)	1890-1958
1890	Walther Eichrodt	1916	1916	1960		German Old Testament scholar and Protestant theologian	1890-1978
1890	George Remington Havens	1917	1917	1961		American professor of French	1890-1977
1890	Hilma Granqvist	1918	1932	1958		Finnish Swedish-speaking anthropologist (studies of Palestinians)	1890-1972
1890	Nathaniel Peffer	1918	No	1958		American researcher of Far East problems	1890-1964
1890	Rosalind Moss	1922	No	1970		British Egyptologist and bibliographer	1890-1990
1890	Eric Dingwall	1922	1929	1956		British anthropologist, psychical researcher and librarian	1890-1986
1890	James Philip Mills	1922	No	1953		British member of the Indian Civil Service and an ethnographer	1890-1960
1890	André Vaillant	1924	1928	1966		French linguist, philologist and grammarian who specialized in Slavic languages	1890-1977
1890	Olga Freidenberg	1924	1924	1950 w		Russian classical philologist, one of the pioneers of cultural studies in Russia	1890-1955

1890	Suniti Kumar Chatterji	1926	1926	1952	Indian linguist, educationist and litterateur	1890-1977
1890	John Rupert Firth	1930		1956	British English linguist and a leading figure in British linguistics during the 1950s	1890-1960
1890	William H. Wiser	1930	1933	1959	American anthropologist, and a Fourth Presbyterian Church	1890-1961
1890	Ervin Baktay	1933	1933	1958	Hungarian painter, art historian, orientalist, astrologer, writer, literary translator	1890-1963
1890	Boris Mouravieff	1949		1962	Russian historian, philosopher, writer and university professor	1890-1966
1891	Pere Bosch-Gimpera	1911	1911	1974	Spanish-Mexican archaeologist and anthropologist	1891-1974
1891	Gerard Clauson	1912		1951	British civil servant, businessman, and Orientalist best known for his studies of the Turkic languages	1891-1974
1891	Hermann Poppelbaum	1913		1963	German anthropologist, psychologist, philosopher, anthroposophist, teacher and author	1891-1979
1891	Viktor Zhirmunsky	1913		1971	Russian literary historian and linguist	1891-1971
1891	Karl Ludwig Schmidt	1913	1913	1953	German Protestant theologian and professor of New Testament studies	1891-1956
1891	Otto Regenbogen	1914	1914	1959	German linguist and scholar	1891-1966
1891	Robert Bleichsteiner	1914	1914	1954	Austrian ethnologist	1891-1954
1891	Otto Regenbogen	1914	1914	1959	German linguist and scholar	1891-1966
1891	Albert C. Baugh	1915	1915	1961	American professor of English(author of a textbook for History of the English language ("HEL" at U.S. universities))	1891-1981
1891	William F. Albright	1916	1916	1958	American archaeologist, biblical scholar, philologist, and expert on ceramics	1891-1971
1891	John Layard	1916		1956	British anthropologist and psychologist	1891-1974
1891	Hu Shih	1917	1917	1962	Chinese philosopher, essayist and diplomat	1891-1962
1891	Anna Bērzkalne	1917	1917	1951 w	Latvian teacher and folklorist who founded the Archives of Latvian Folklore	1891-1956
1891	James Conway Davies	1918	1918	1960	British Welsh historian and palaeographer	1891-1971
1891	Paulina Lebl-Albala	1919		1947	Serbian feminist, translator, literary critic, literature theoretician, and professor of literature	1891-1967
1891	Marie Delcourt	1919	1919	1961 w	Belgian classical philologist	1891-1979
1891	Hans Kurath	1920	1920	1962	Czech-American linguist (American English)	1891-1992
1891	Milan Budimir	1920	1920	1962	Serbian classical scholar	1891-1975

1891	Cyril W. Beaumont	1920		1965	British dance historian, critic, technical theorist, translator, bookseller, and publisher	1891-1976
1891	Rudolf Carnap	1921	1921	1961	German language philisopher (Logic, Epistemology, Philosophy of science, Semantics)	1891-1970
1891	Linda Fierz-David	1922		1955 w	German philologist and one of the first Jungian analysts	1891-1955
1891	A. P. Elkin	1922		1956	Australian Anglican clergyman, an influential Australian anthropologist during the mid twentieth century and a proponent of the assimilation of Indigenous Australians	1891-1979
1891	Pierre Fouché	1924		1962	French romanist, catalanist and phonetician	1891-1967
1891	Mariya Yefimovna Sergeyenko	1926	No	1964 w	Ukrainian-Soviet scholar of Roman history and philologist	1891-1987
1891	Georges Duthuit	1926		1973	French writer, art critic and historian	1891-1973
1891	Clive Harcourt Carruthers	1929	No	1961	Canadian classicist	1891-1980
1891	Marie Inez Hilger	1934	1939	1975 w	American Benedictine nun and anthropologist who was the first woman admitted to the Catholic University of America in Washington, D.C.	1891-1977
1892	Jean Bayet	1912	1926	1960	French Latinist	1892-1969
1892	Erich Auerbach	1913	1921	1957	German philologist and comparative scholar and critic of literature	1892-1957
1892	Helmuth Plessner	1913		1959	German philosopher and sociologist, and a primary advocate of "philosophical anthropology"	1892-1985
1892	Hellmut Ritter	1914	1914	1969	German Orientalist specialising in Arabic, Persian, and Turkish, and an authority on Sufi ritual and mystical beliefs	1892-1971
1892	István Hajnal	1914		1950	Hungarian social historian and palaeographer	1892-1956
1892	Jan Stanisław Bystroń	1914	1914	1963	Polish ethnographer who studied the Kurpie	1892-1964
1892	Erwin Panofsky	1914	1914	1962	German Jewish art historian	1892-1968
1892	Fernand Mossé	1914	1938	1956	French philologist and historian, specialized in Germanic languages and German literature	1892-1956
1892	Chao Yuen Ren	1915	1918	1960	Chinese-American linguist (modern study of Chinese phonology and grammar), educator, scholar, poet, and composer)	1892-1982

1892	W. Norman Brown	1916	1916	1954	American distinguished Indologist and Sanskritist who established the first academic department of South Asian Studies in North America and organized the American Oriental Society in 1926	1892-1975
1892	V. Gordon Childe	1916	1916	1956	Australian archaeologist who specialised in the study of European prehistory	1892-1957
1892	Augusto Rostagni	1916		1961	Italian classical philologist	1892-1961
1892	Philip Ainsworth Means	1917	No	1944	American-Peruvian anthropologist and historian	1892-1944
1892	Erik Ahlman	1918	1919	1952	Finish philosopher and linguist	1892-1952
1892	Newman Ivey White	1918	1918	1948	American professor of English	1892-1948
1892	Godfrey Rolles Driver	1918		1962	British Orientalist noted for his studies of Semitic languages and Assyriology	1892-1975
1892	Georg Morgenstierne	1918	1918	1962	Norwegian professor of linguistics (Indo-Iranian languages)	1892-1978
1892	Domenico Vittorini	1919	1919	1958	Italian-American academic	1892-1958
1892	Walter Benjamin	1919	1919	1940	German Jewish philosopher, cultural critic and essayist	1892-1940
1892	Gerhard Rohlfs	1920	1920	1957	German linguist, Romanist	1892-1986
1892	Marion Elizabeth Blake	1921	1921	1961	w American classical languages professor	1892-1961
1892	Samuel Kirkland Lothrop	1921	1921	1958	American archaeologist and anthropologist who specialized in Central and South American Studies	1892-1965
1892	Alfred Irving Hallowell	1924	1924	1971	American anthropologist, archaeologist and businessman	1892-1974
1892	Samuel Gili Gaya	1924	1924	1958	Spanish Romanist, Hispanist and Lexicographer	1892-1976
1892	Homer H. Dubs	1925	1925	1959	American sinologist and polymath	1892-1969
1892	Nikolai Nevsky	1926	1935	1937	Russian linguist, and expert of East Asian languages (founders of the modern study of the Tangut language of the mediaeval Xi Xia Empire)	1892-1937
1892	Charlotte Viall Wiser	1930	1933	1961	w American anthropologist, and a Presbyterian rural-missionary to North India – Uttar Pradesh	1892-1981
1893	Kaj Birket-Smith	1916	1937	1977	Danish philologist and anthropologist	1893-1977
1893	Clement Martyn Doke	1917	1925	1953	South African linguist (African languages)	1893-1980
1893	Phyllis Ackerman	1917	1917	1956	w American art historian	1893-1977
1893	Carl E. Guthe	1917	1917	1953	American academic and anthropologist	1893-1974

1893	Gilbert Seldes	1917		1963	American journalist, music and drama critic, author and playwright	1893-1970
1893	Eugénie Droz	1918	1923	1963 w	Swiss romance scholar, editor publisher and writer	1893-1976
1893	Bekir Vaap oğlu Çobanzade	1919	1919	1937	Ukrainian (Crimean Tatar) poet and professor of Turkic languages	1893-1937
1893	Gustav Natvig-Pedersen	1919	1919	1965	Norwegian philologist, educator and politician for the Labour Party	1893-1965
1893	Eugen Dieth	1919	1919	1956	Swiss linguist, phonetician and dialectologist	1893-1956
1893	Mikhail Tikhomirov	1919		1965	Russian specialist in medieval Russian paleography	1893-1965
1893	Johannes Friedrich	1920		1966	German hittitologist (archaeology, history, philology, and art history of the Hittite civilisation)	1893-1972
1893	Louise Adams Holland	1920	1920	1964 w	American philologist, university teacher, academic and archaeologist	1893-1990
1893	Mieczysław Gębarowicz	1921	1921	1962	Polish art historian, soldier, dissident, museum director and custodian of cultural heritage	1893-1984
1893	Emma Adelaide Hahn	1922	1929	1963 w	American linguist and classicist who specialized in Latin grammar and Indo-European linguistics	1893-1967
1893	Ralph Linton	1922	1925	1953	American respected American anthropologist of the mid-20th century	1893-1953
1893	Joseph Twadell Shipley	1923	1931	1957	American drama critic, author, editor and associate professor of English	1893-1988
1893	Erwin Ramsdell Goodenough	1923	1923	1962	American scholar in the history of religion	1893-1965
1893	Jakob Rosenberg	1923	1923	1964	German-American art historian and Rembrandt scholar	1893-1980
1893	Gladys Reichard	1925	1925	1955 w	American anthropologist and linguist	1893-1955
1893	Laura Veccia Vaglieri	1925	No	1974 w	Italian orientalist	1893-1989
1893	Elizabeth du Gué Trapier	1925		1972 w	Spanish art expert	1893-1974
1893	Otto Pretzl	1926	1926	1941	German Arabist-orientalist, who specialized in Koranic studies	1893-1941
1893	Constantin Brăiloiu	1927		1958	Romanian composer and internationally known ethnomusicologist	1893-1958
1893	John Martin	1928		1962	American America's first major dance critic	1893-1985
1893	William Hung	1928	1940	1980	Chinese historian and sinologist	1893-1980

1893 Ernst Manker	1929		1961	Swedish ethnographer, known for his work on Sami history and ethnography	1893-1972
1893 W Dingliang	1932		1966	Chinese pioneering Chinese anthropologist and educator	1893-1969
1893 Andrew Nelson	1938	1938	1975	American missionary and scholar of East Asian languages and literature (Japanese lexicography)	1893-1975
1893 Harold E. Lambert	1939	No	1950	British linguist and anthropologist in Kenya	1893-1967
1894 Giuseppe Tucci	1911	1913	1969	Italian Orientalist, Indologist and scholar of East Asian studies, specialised in Tibetan culture and history of Buddhism	1894-1984
1894 Paul Demiéville	1914	1914	1964	Swiss-French sinologist and Orientalist (studies of the Dunhuang manuscripts and Buddhism, translations of Chinese poetry)	1894-1979
1894 Henry Courtenay Fenn	1915		1962	American sinologist and architect of Yale University's Chinese language program	1894-1978
1894 Gertrud Herzog-Hauser	1916	1916	1950 w	Austrian classical philologist	1894-1953
1894 Martin Sommerfeld	1916	1916	1939	German-American professor of German language and literature	1894-1939
1894 Marija Kon	1916	1916	1967	Bosnian Germanist and the first woman in Bosnia and Herzegovina to be awarded a doctorate	1894-1987
1894 Emil Forrer	1917	1917	1944	Swiss Assyriologist and pioneering Hittitologist	1894-1986
1894 Winifred Lamb	1918	1940	1958 w	British archaeologist, art historian, and museum curator who specialised in Greek, Roman, and Anatolian cultures and artefacts	1894-1963
1894 Claudiu Isopescu	1919	1919	1956	Romanian literary historian and translator	1894-1956
1894 Farkas Gyula	1919	1919	1958	German-Hungarian literary historian and Finno-Ugric linguist	1894-1958
1894 Mark Van Doren	1920	1920	1959	American poet, writer and critic	1894-1972
1894 Paul Wittek	1920	1920	1961	Austrian Orientalist and historian	1894-1978
1894 Ludwig Bachhofer	1921	1921	1965	German art historian	1894-1976
1894 Friedrich Klingner	1921	1921	1963	German classical philologist	1894-1968
1894 Cecile O'Rahilly	1922	No	1964 w	Irish scholar of the Celtic languages	1894-1980
1894 Walter Silz	1922	1922	1961	American professor of German language and literature	1894-1980
1894 Max Weinreich	1923	1923	1954	Latvian the Jewish linguist (sociolinguistics and Yiddish)	1894-1969

1894	Otto J. Maenchen-Helfen	1923	1923	1962	Austrian academic, sinologist, historian, author, and traveler	1894-1969
1894	Frederick Bodmer	1924	1924	1955	Swiss philologist	1894-1960
1894	Jost Trier	1924	1924	1943	German Germanic linguist and Medievalist	1894-1970
1894	Johann Fück	1925	1925	1962	German orientalist	1894-1974
1894	Luther Carrington Goodrich	1929	1934	1961	American sinologist and historian of China	1894-1986
1894	Agnès Humbert	1936		1959	French art historian, ethnographer	1894-1963